

Selective extractions for trace element determination in black shales from Dehradun area

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Abstract : The study focuses on the leaching of trace elements (Co, Cr, Cu, Mo, Ni, Pb, U, V and Zn) present in black shale in Loharka, Dehradun. Samples of non-weathered, weathered and burnt black shale were chemically characterized and the potential element release from these has been assessed by using standard water-based leaching tests and leaching using acids and oxidising agents. Chemical extractions provide further information on the phases wherein elements are bound in shale samples. Results show that the shale samples analysed are rich in Ni (50–300 ppm), Cu (10–150 ppm), Mo (64–500 ppm), U (40–70 ppm), Zn (20–300 ppm) and V (100–2300 ppm), respectively. Mo bound mainly in sulphides or organic matter is very labile (20% leachability) with water as extractant. Co and Zn are leached completely with acids and per-oxodisulphate. The overall conclusion is that black shale shows a high potential for releasing Cu, Mo, Ni, U, V and Zn during weathering. The leaching of trace elements using different extractants under different conditions give complete recovery and therefore can be adopted as fast and rapid analytical methodology for the determination of these trace elements.

Keywords : Black shale, leaching of trace elements, microwave digestion, ICP-OES, AAS.

Introduction

Black shale can be enriched in many trace elements and also in sulphides. Black shales with high concentrations of trace elements are significant in environmental geochemistry. They are easily weathered and weathering of black shales can therefore potentially contaminate soils and waters, in a manner similar to metal leaching from acid sulphate soils. In this study, laboratory leaching procedures has been carried out to assess the leachability of different elements in black shale from a Dehradun area in Uttarakhand. The trace elements, Cu, Mo, Ni, Pb, U, V and Zn occur at high levels in the black shales.

Chemical analysis of black shales is applied : (1) to investigate the concentration of potentially toxic elements in the rock-soil system from areas underlain by black shales and slates; (2) to evaluate the level of enrichment of potentially toxic elements in soils derived from black shales and slates and (3) to identify uranium-bearing minerals in black shales.

Inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry has been largely acknowledged and extensively used in the multi-elemental analysis of geological samples¹⁻⁴.

More recently, inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry is being progressively applied in the analysis of geological materials for the determination of trace/ultra trace elements^{5,6}.

The present work deals with the studies pertaining to extraction of different trace elements in black shale samples from Dehradun area. The leachability of trace elements gives simple and rapid analytical methodology for the determination of various trace elements in black shales. Trace elements like Co and Zn can be determined completely by HNO₃ and H₂O₂ leaching while V, Mo, Cu, Ni, Pb, Sr can be determined using microwave digestion system for dissolution. .

Experimental

Instrumentation and instrumental parameters :

HORIBA JOBIN YVON ICP-OES Model JY 2000-2 with 40.68 MHz solid state generator, 640 cm focal length monochromator equipped with 4320 grooves/mm holographic ion-etched grating with Glass concentric nebulizer.

An Analytik Jena (Model novAA 300, Germany)

Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) was used for the determination of Cu, Co, Ni, Zn, Pb, Sr, Ba etc.

The microwave digestion system CEM MARS-5 was used to carry out digestion of the samples.

All the equipments were used as per manufacturer's prescribed procedure.

Reagents and standards :

Millipore Ultrapure water was used throughout the analysis. All other reagents and acids were of AR grade. Individual standard stock solution of all the trace elements were prepared by using analytical grade compounds.

Extraction procedure :

Seven different procedures were adopted for extraction/dissolution of the samples 0.2 g to 0.5 g of sample was placed in five different 100 ml beakers and was treated by different 50 ml of extractants : (A) distilled water, (B) 20% HNO₃, (C) mixture of 20% HNO₃ and 10% H₂O₂, (D) 20% ammonium peroxodisulphate solution and (E) 10% ammonium acetate and heated to 150 °C for 2 h. All the solutions were filtered and made up to the mark in 50 ml volumetric flask.

Microwave digestion using HNO₃ and H₂O₂ :

In another set of experimentations : 0.1 g to 0.2 g of sample was taken in a XP-1500 plus high pressure digestion vessel followed by addition of 8 ml of 10% HNO₃ and 1 ml of 5% H₂O₂. The closed vessels were run in microwave digestion system as per the programme. The cooled

samples were filtered and made upto 50 ml.

A 0.5 g sample of black shales (200 mesh) is initially subjected to ignition in a platinum dish and the sample solution is obtained by repeated evaporation with HF-HNO₃ and then evaporation with HNO₃ (to remove fluoride). The sample is digested with HNO₃ and boiled to get a clear solution. If a residue is remained, it is fuse with sodium carbonate. It is finally dissolved in HNO₃ and both the solutions are added and made up to 100 ml.

Samples were taken in duplicate and triplicate analysis was carried out both in ICP-OES and AAS.

Results and discussion

Different components of organic matter present in the shales namely tannic acid has been found to reduce Fe and Mn while peat, lignin and humic acid (components of organic matter) have been shown to reduce uranium, molybdenum and vanadium into more soluble forms. Metal may also form soluble complexes or colloidal suspensions with organic acids (fraction of black shale). Humic acid rapidly decompose sulphides by forming soluble metal compounds. Metal-humic complexes in natural water have greater stability. The leachability of different trace elements were studied using different chemical extractants and the results obtained are given in Table 1. The major matrix composition and the trace element concentration of the shale samples analysed from Dehradun area given in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

Table 1. Comparison of leachability of trace elements in black shales using different extractant

Sample no.	V (ppm)							%	Mo (ppm)							%
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G		RSD	A	B	C	D	E	F	
AMD-1	10	1432	1035	227	<10	2103	2182	0.4-2.4	27	100	100	93	23	130	133	2.5-4.0
AMD-2	<10	521	424	113	<10	1215	1260	0.4-2.8	31	108	116	107	14	149	158	2.1-4.8
AMD-3	<10	165	133	46	<10	330	326	1.1-4.0	9	387	393	360	61	466	482	1.3-4.1
AMD-4	<10	1161	765	256	<10	2295	2264	0.3-1.8	24	137	137	124	58	195	197	2.5-4.0
AMD-5	<10	892	739	227	<10	1805	1872	0.5-1.5	26	170	170	152	40	220	224	
Sample no.	Co (ppm)							%	Cu (ppm)							%
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G		RSD	A	B	C	D	E	F	
AMD-1	<10	40	38	40	15	38	41	3.1-4.2	<10	48	52	48	<10	55	66	3.5-4.2
AMD-2	<10	33	38	40	18	36	35	3.0-4.2	<10	26	30	26	<10	36	44	4.0-4.5
AMD-3	<10	32	31	26	<10	30	31	3.5-4.5	<10	91	91	79	<10	96	111	2.5-3.7
AMD-4	<10	71	77	70	40	74	72	2.8-4.0	<10	20	20	17	<10	30	48	4.0-5.0
AMD-5	<10	57	60	54	25	53	55	2.8-4.0	<10	32	34	29	<10	42	60	3.3-4.5

Table-1 (contd.)

Sample no.	Cr (ppm)							%	Ba (ppm)							%
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G		RSD	A	B	C	D	E	F	
AMD-1	<10	38	39	10	<10	52	156	2.3-4.6	<10	164	179	15	106	209	538	1.4-4.2
AMD-2	<10	22	22	<10	11	29	126	2.5-4.8	<10	527	576	17	491	602	1028	0.8-4.1
AMD-3	<10	32	29	<10	<10	42	102	2.6-3.8	<10	496	492	27	224	552	598	1.3-4.2
AMD-4	<10	38	35	14	<10	45	310	1.5-4.0	<10	339	325	23	101	355	448	1.5-4.1
AMD-5	<10	37	38	15	<10	54	318	1.5-4.1	<10	368	380	28	94	388	444	1.3-3.8

Sample no.	Sr (ppm)							%	Zn (ppm)							%
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G		RSD	A	B	C	D	E	F	
AMD-1	<10	17	17	13	12	20	24	4.0-5.9	8	27	28	28	20	23	24	4.1-6.0
AMD-2	<10	23	22	17	22	25	35	4.0-5.8	4	32	36	35	11	35	36	4.0-5.8
AMD-3	<10	33	31	25	11	33	36	3.5-5.8	7	221	220	208	11	217	222	2.4-5.7
AMD-4	<10	12	10	<10	<10	12	13	4.1-5.9	10	59	52	48	11	52	55	4.1-5.7
AMD-5	<10	16	19	12	<10	17	18	4.1-5.9	15	88	90	85	8	95	100	4.2-5.9

A - Extraction using water, B - Extraction using 20% HNO₃, C - Extraction using 20% HNO₃ and 10% H₂O₂, D - Extraction using 20% ammonium peroxodisulphate, E - Extraction using 10% ammonium acetate, F - Microwave digestion using HNO₃ and H₂O₂, G - Sample dissolution using HF/HNO₃.

Table 2. Whole rock analysis of the black shale samples

Sl. no.	Sample no.	SiO ₂ (%)	TiO ₂ (%)	Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	Fe (T) as Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	MnO (%)	MgO (%)	CaO (%)	Na ₂ O (%)	K ₂ O (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (%)	LOI (%)
1.	AMD-1	56.43	0.98	14.49	3.66	0.03	2.2	3.33	1.07	3.91	0.07	11.24
2.	AMD-2	56.61	1.03	14.13	2.53	0.02	2.05	3.42	2.07	4.81	0.06	12.32
3.	AMD-3	55.43	0.81	15.41	5.61	0.01	1.48	2.94	2.21	3.76	0.56	10.82
4.	AMD-4	60.94	0.77	13.85	2.14	<0.01	1.54	1.22	1.35	5.01	0.11	12.41
5.	AMD-5	58.32	0.81	15.39	4.09	0.01	1.52	1.24	1.39	4.81	0.11	12.22

Table 3. Trace element composition of black shale samples

Sl. no.	Sample no.	Cr	Ni	Co	Cu	Zn	Pb	Rb	Ba	Sr	Mo	V	Cd	Li	Zr	Th
1.	AMD-1	156	218	41	66	24	<50	99	538	24	133	2182	<10	19	89	10
2.	AMD-2	126	140	30	44	36	<50	112	1028	35	158	1260	<10	25	97	11
3.	AMD-3	102	266	21	111	222	<50	117	598	36	482	326	<10	14	112	12
4.	AMD-4	310	180	72	48	55	<50	118	448	13	197	2264	<10	<10	75	<10
5.	AMD-5	318	311	55	60	100	<50	117	444	18	224	1872	<10	11	70	<10

It was also observed that traces like Cu, Ni, Pb, Mo, V, Sr were leached from 50 to 80% using the different extractants but, the recovery becomes complete by microwave digestion using HNO₃/H₂O₂. Traces like Cr, Ba were not completely recovered even by microwave digestion system.

The high extraction of trace elements in black shales from Dehradun area also signifies that these trace ele-

ments are not associated with silicate matrix but they are loosely bound or adsorbed on the surface. The availability of various traces also determines the provenance from which these black shales are formed.

Conclusion

Black shales from Dehradun area are rich in many trace elements such as Mo, V, Zn, Ni, Cu etc. The leach-

ing tests showed that some elements, occurring in high concentrations in the shale, could be easily mobilised on oxidation. A test using only water as extraction medium was sufficient to cause considerable immediate leaching of Mo from the unoxidised shale material. Mo bound in sulphides and organic matter is easily extracted, nearly 20% with just water. Another test, using leaching with acids, per-oxodisulphate, combination of HNO₃ acid and hydrogen peroxide, showed that Mo, Cr, V, Co, Zn, Ni, U and Cu are elements that in longer term can be leached in considerable amounts from the shale material. Various extraction procedures applied showed that acid leaching extracted nearly 60–80% of Mo, Sr and V. Co and Zn are extracted completely by acids, ammonium peroxodisulphate and H₂O₂. Cu and Ni are also extracted 50–70% by acid leaching. Ba and Cr are not easily extracted showing that they are locked in silicate matrix. U is extracted completely by acids, HNO₃ and H₂O₂, ammonium peroxodisulphate etc.

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